

ABOUT SUSTAINABLE SOCIAL SYSTEM TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract

The paper is devoted to fundamental issues concerning the ideology of the future social progress. Its implementation has available in the first place basing on the recognized framework concept of sustainable development (SD). At the same time, this concept requires serious improvement. A realistic design of institutional changes in connection with resource and organizational/behavioral changes needed for SD is called for to realize in the line of overall social system transformation. Its adequate understanding presupposes an exhaustive study of interconnected transformations in the main social fields as system processes taking into account the influence of relatively exogenous factors (technological, demographic and climate changes).

According to the author's argument, the sustainable reproduction of the economy of a mature post-industrial type, including the green sectors, implies its stable and quiet growth, although the rapid growth of individual markets, especially innovative ones, may take place. Also, without any alternative, the formation at the global level of a multipolar political order when approving the international legal regime. At the same time, national elites will significantly replenish due to represents of high management in the innovative and high-tech sectors, while the presence of leaders of financial and trade capital will reduce. In addition, sustainable social system transformation characterizes by the equitable distribution of wealth in its broad sense (including the consumption of natural and cultural goods, education) among all people's generations accompanied by constant increase in the quality of life, the improvement of the status pyramid and the strengthening of solidarity.

To sum up: sustainable overall social transformation in its main interconnected areas looks like an indispensable attribute of the future human progress.

Key words: *sustainable development, social system, system transformation, adaptation to technologies.*

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The great desire, as if to counterbalance the unfavorable conjuncture of this day's world development, concludes to present the prospect of a positive global future, albeit achievable through overcoming difficult obstacles. Let us at least partially expose this idea.

1. A conceptual vision of overall social progress

Until recently, world development in the present post crisis decade has characterized by a lack of significant technological and institutional progress. In the current period, the growth of capital in conventional markets is the most significant factor of economic development in almost all developed countries. Macro effect of growth of existing high-tech and knowledge-intensive capital and, in particular, investments in information technology of today's generation actually reached saturation for a long time ago. In general, an almost gloomy picture of the stagnation of technological and institutional progress has taken place, judging, at least, from the dynamics of indicators recognized at the international level - total or multi-factor productivity. In fact, the inertial trend of economic development unambiguously prevails.

The phenomenon of the world migration tide, which exceeded 3% of the total population of the planet, is still stunning. Fundamentally it is due to the gap between consumer and cultural demands and the opportunities for their satisfaction of citizens of poor and, especially, of crisis countries. Visiting many countries one can see an excessive influx of migrants in relation to the needs of the national economy, given the downswing in economic globalization. The disproportion between the ever-expanding wave of world migration, on the one hand, and the slow growth of global and multi-regional markets, along with stagnation and even a decline in the scope of foreign direct investment, on the other, is becoming ever more threatening.

Under such circumstances, the second advent of neoconservative capitalism, oriented to the maximum turnover and profitability of national private capital in traditional, non-high-technology and non-science-intensive sectors, seems quite understandable. In turn, the implementation of these goals well combines with economic nationalism creating the conditions for the maximum competitiveness of producers in respective countries.

By all accounts, the American mono hegemony has irretrievably gone to the past. However, we can ascertain, in the geopolitical space the factor of force, which determines the disgust anomalies at the interstate level, is definitely prevailing. Consequently, the pessimistic expectations of the unconditional transformation of the factor of power into the dominant in international relations and the complete restoration of the hegemonic duopoly including the United States and its closest allies, on the one hand, and China-Russia, on the other, are understandable. Then there will be a split of the world, in the institutional sense more profound in comparison with the era of confrontation between the Western and Socialist blocs in 1960-1980.

Without exaggeration, the world community and the majority of its members - sovereign countries - face a choice of urgent and fully realistic long-term solutions that allow them to concentrate their efforts on overcoming the arisen barriers to progress. To justify these decisions, it is necessary to take into account a whole series of processes of economic and other social changes associated with fundamental, not short-term structural shifts - technological, resource, organizational and, of course, institutional.

In view of what has been said, it seems reasonable to refer to the theory of social system transformation, relying on recognized outstanding contributions [Polany 1944, Parsons 1962, Giddens 1984, Luhmann 1995]. In accordance with this theory the research paradigm, concluding in the treatment of the development of the social system as a transformation of its multidimensional structure, is legitimate. This approach assumes an integrative representation of the significant components of the development vector of a particular society as a social system in a real time-space dimension.

Transformation of the social system in its traditional (narrow) understanding encompasses the main fields of social action, economic, political and societal (status), characterized by the existence of a defined institutional design and resource provision. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account that social changes in institutionally structured fields have inevitably accompanied in large degree by non-institutionalized processes of technological, demographic and climate changes.

Thus, social system transformation occurs in a result of the interaction of endogenous institutional/resource shifts. As well as a variety of exogenous processes. Such as the invention of fundamentally new technologies, the change of cycles of solar activity, etc.

The initial premise of the system transformation concept of progress development lies in the permanent change of production, personal and social needs, based on achievable new resource, institutional and technological capabilities, expected demographic and climatic changes [Martynov 2016]. These requirements, in turn, predetermine the multi sector vector of potential economic output and the vectors of long-term shifts needed in other fields of social action. They are the objective guidelines for the fundamental development of the social macros as an integral system, in the direction of which, under the necessary conditions, the desired transformational transformations can occur in accordance with the criteria of progress. At first place the criteria for improving well-being in its broadest sense, taking into account the state of the human environment. In accordance with the internationally recognized position, the integrative welfare of the society has reflected in the indices of the quality of life and human development as so as in the happiness indices, evaluation and country comparison of which has become widespread.

Without resorting to obvious mathematical proofs, one can assert. Grounded on the well-known criteria of optimal inter-temporal ratio of costs and results, the transformation of social macros as a system on a stable and plausible long-term trajectory is preferable. Its immanent fea-

ture is not a spasmodic, but a steadily consistent movement to the achievable transformation boundaries, based on the identified opportunities.

Thus, in order to justify the concept of future social progress, it is logical to call for a universal idea of integrative sustainable development, moreover, as applied to the system (precisely system!) transformation of the whole society. Following this approach, an inalienable feature of the desired development of society as an all-encompassing social system refers to a sustainable transformation. It expresses in the reproduction of the promising development vectors of the overall social system, which, according to the recognized criteria, believed to be sustainability acceptable.

Judging by the harsh contemporary realities, with respect to the national interests of individual countries the imperative of sustainability has most clearly manifested in the guarantee of maintaining an acceptable quality of life and well-being levels. This is attainable through the interaction of all public forces, including corporate and other businesses. Nevertheless, the main responsibility in the constant ensuring the sustainability of the national development results put unequivocally on the state.

This role of the state as a guarantor of sustainable development is definitely incompatible with neo-liberalism, as well as with the neo-conservative capitalist doctrine. The same concerns the ideology of modern corporatism. The effect of charitable activities, called socially responsible, of large corporations is inevitably limited.

It makes sense to clarify. The desired transformation of society is not fully exhausted by the processes of sustainable change. It can include processes of more progressive changes that act as the results of initiative decisions of purely market agents and social entrepreneurs under the condition that sustainable development trajectories prevail in the main fields of social actions.

Undoubtedly, the indicated initial approach to the design of future social progress should be based on the framework concept of sustainable development (SD), long ago recognized by the international community [Enders and Remig 2015]. Its latest version has presented in the official memorandum "Transformation of our world: An Agenda for Sustainable Development for 2030" or simply an Agenda adopted at a special UN summit in September 2015. The Agenda addresses equally to the developed, post-developing and developing countries.

As is known, the UN framework concept of SD is integrative. Achieving the set goals in principle supposes to be equally priority and interdependent within the 15-year perspective (2016-2030).

The fundamental innovation concludes in the statement of the imperative to create effective institutions at all levels, recorded in Agenda Goal 16. Almost decisive for successful integrative SD, according to the adepts of the renewed concept, acquires the phenomenon of the spread of inclusive institutions [Global Sustainable 2016]. These institutions, mostly based on the prin-

ciples of universality and non-discrimination, provide equal rights and opportunities for producers and consumers, as well as access to all resources and services. They are confronted by exclusive institutions that ensure the withdrawal of resources in favor of groups that have economic and political power at the expense of the rest of society [Acemogly et al 2015].

As stressed in the Memorandum of the G-20 Summit in China [G20 Action Plan 2016], the necessary step concludes in approving a suitable institutional environment for inclusive non-dependent business including social entrepreneurship. Exactly the inclusive business is called upon to play a key role in implementing the imperatives of future sustainable development.

At the same time, according to many researchers (the author among them), the current concept of SD is selectively segmental and in fact far from the system one. It mainly focuses on environmental and humanitarian issues, the conservation of natural resources and the use of reproducible resources, overcoming the consequences of climate degradation, improving the efficiency of individual institutions. Opposite to it, the problems of fundamental institutional reforms and adaptation to fundamental technological changes have been only fixed using previous traditional formulations. Namely from the resolution of these problems, the possibility of achieving sustainable acceptable production, consumption and employment trajectories depends to the greatest extent, as well as achieving purely ecological, climate and humanitarian targets.

In our opinion, the treatment of inclusive institutions, represented by the adherents of the framework concept, also needs a serious adjustment. It should be borne in mind that not all effective institutions needed for sustainable development are inclusive; moreover, not all can be incorporated into the framework of contractual relations. What has been said above primarily concerns the institutions of public regulation. Many of them, in principle, are not inclusive, such as progressive taxation rules. Also, key institutions that function in corporate and other limited competition markets, a number of informal political institutions and, to a large extent, informal social norms conditioned by the specifics of national development are definitely not inclusive.

Even more significantly, the describing concept in question is not essentially a transformational one in the institutional projection. The desired patterns of inclusive institutions as if have a priori fixed, although their development supposes largely due to a purposeful policy of the state on different fields of social action.

Proceeding from the above argumentation, the realistic design of institutional changes in connection with resource and organizational-behavioral changes needed for sustainable development is called to base on an exhaustive view of transformations in the main social fields. In line with the overall social system transformation, the time-space positioning of institutional and resource changes taking into account the influence of institutional/resource changes on the "adjacent" fields of social actions and relatively exogenous factors (technological, demographic and climate changes). As a result, an adequate reflection of the integrative transformation of the entire vector of parameters of the social system becomes possible, proceeding from the imperatives

of sustainable development. Besides, it worth noting, the attainment of ecological improvements and relative climate stabilization depends on an assumed integrative consequence of transformational shifts in all areas of social activity.

Apparently, the main two criteria signs of sustainable social system transformation at the national, regional and global levels can formulate in the following way. First, the formation of stable long-term trajectories of the main resource for the future, reflecting the entire set of environmental, special humanitarian and other parameters of sustainable development. Second, reliable adaptation to the expected technological, demographic and climate changes insofar as they act as exogenous factors with respect to the transformation of the entire social system and its main components.

At the same time, one cannot fail to take into account the existence of a huge number of processes of non-stable changes, bearing in mind at least cyclical fluctuations of the market situation, the impact of technological shocks, sporadic political perturbations and social conflicts. They can be count-progressive and have a very significant impact on economic, political and societal fundamental changes, leading to a violation of the conditions for a stable system transformation. Therefore, apparently, the problem of neutralizing such influence in the future will be central to the design of directly long-term strategic solutions and mechanisms for overcoming emerging risks [Transformation towards 2018].

Constructive position concludes in achieving a stable progressive world development at the main social fields as an inalienable condition for the appropriate transition to the trajectory of global sustainable progress. This position on the official level actually shares by a significant number, if not majority of the countries in the existing world community. They include almost all countries of continental Europe, China, Japan and Canada, many post developing and developing countries.

Of course, one cannot ignore the fact that the turn to global sustainable progress has become questionable because of the second advent of neoconservative capitalism in the United States. His provisional statement definitely took place. However, according to widely popular belief, in the long term the result of the aggressive course pursued by the US administration will be negative just at the national level. After the exhaustion of the stimulating effect of reducing business taxes and short-term protectionist benefits, a phase of a prolonged recession will take place, taking into account the effect of cyclical factors. As a result, the neoconservative economic and political course, which has a depressingly regressive impact on world development, will come to naught.

And we can hope that soon enough the joint efforts of progressive-led governments of developed and other countries to stabilize the climate, predetermined by the Paris Agreement of 2016, and the improvement of the environment will be crowned with considerable success. Then there will probably be a real world recognition of environmental and other imperatives of sus-

tainable development, ultimately affecting the whole world. A logical consequence of such a global ideological shift will be the perception of choosing the further national development path along the line of a sustainable social system transformation.

Let us try to imagine at least a sketch vision of the future sustainable overall social system transformation along its three main directions - economic, political and societal.

2. Sustainable economic system transformation

The expected future changes in the early twenties will lead to a rethinking of the understanding of sustainable economic development as an uninterrupted time-space transformational process. The most significant contribution to the economic output is called upon to make cumulative technological and institutional progress. It acts as the main means of ensuring the long-term competitiveness of national economies, but not the aggressive protectionist policy following the current American model.

The unfolding of new industrialization opens the way for the maximum reduction in the consumption of hydrocarbons and other renewable resources and their replacement by reproducible green technologies in the grandiose dissemination and the implementation of efficient infrastructure projects, specifically on environmental criteria. Consequently, the desired significant effect of decoupling will be achieved, when economic results grow much faster than consumption of resources and the scale of their impact on the environment.

Apparently, on a global scale, there will be a long-awaited structural shift towards the prevalence of innovative and high-tech economic sectors, where reproducible resources and energy efficient, waste-free and low-waste, technologies will be used. In addition, we can expect the establishment of a green economy in most of the world that meets the imperatives of environmental sustainability and climate improvement. Already there is a significant number of economically and environmentally effective "green" technologies ready for widespread use. This gives grounds to hope for a gradual (just gradual!) elimination of the existing "brown economy". A long-awaited consequence of a drastic reduction in the consumption of non-renewable resources will be the conservation of biodiversity and the enhancement of natural capital based on the restoration of ecosystems and spread of new ones.

At the same time, it is definitely unacceptable to simplify the problem of market adaptation to new technologies in the incoming future. As evidenced by numerous facts, the use of a number of new technologies, including digital technologies, in principle does not meet the criterion of economic stability. Quite likely the shock effect of the development of individual markets, where these technologies are implemented. According to a number of researchers, the consequences of robotization and the use of technologies based on artificial intelligence will have a very painful impact on labor markets.

In the long term, there will be a long-term need for the creation of special regulatory mechanisms. At first place, it implies the application directly in the market environment of new social technologies, which are beginning to be developed.

The very important imperative of a sustainable system transformation in the future is the maintenance of employment in the market and social sectors in full accordance with the Agenda. The burning problem of reducing the relative proportion of able-bodied contingent in the population of developed countries due to its aging is likely to be resolved to a significant extent due to the regulated influx of foreign labor on a strictly legal basis.

The future SD is also supposed a fair pay of labor including gender wage equality. If this condition is fulfilled a desired reduction in the differentiation of income and personal/family wealth will be achieved, as it follows from regional studies.

In the observed perspective the increase in the capital and incomes of innovators and high-tech producers can happen to the greatest extent. Conversely, a relative reduction in the capital of financial entities and rental incomes is desirable, accompanied by the elimination of hypertrophied high-yielding components and broad niches for financial speculation. At the same time, an essential condition concludes in maintaining financial balance with reference to individual national economies. Especially in the implementation of future long-term structural reforms [G-20 Enhanced Structural 2016].

According to a number of forecasts, the current regime of a tight monetary stabilization policy will probably also be needed. It should complement by neutralization of illegal / criminal economic activity and anti-corruption course on a recognized legal basis.

At the global, multi-regional and national levels, the assertion as dominant precisely the sustainable economic order is called for. It assumes an unhindered stable trade regime, as well as stable regimes of the international movement of capital in its various forms and labor. Besides, most importantly, acting on the base of coordinated application of global, regional and national legislation. Certainly, it is not compatible with the former liberal (of course, only in words!) international economic order of the era of American hegemony, the return of which is still pinned on by certain backstage circles.

It can be assumed that on the world stage, at least three competing groups of countries will be comparable in market potential: 1) the United States and other countries with the prevailing capitalistic institutional order; 2) China, India, Russia and a number of other non-Western countries; 3) the countries of continental Europe, apparently, in alliance with Japan and Canada. At the same time, the role of regional economic unions, which includes other countries, will remain highly significant. In conditions of strong multilateral international competition there are grounds to assume that most countries will act as equal rights members of the world economic community. In turn, the establishment of such an equal right order will serve as a prerequisite for further movement towards full-scale economic globalization.

Of course, we should not doubt upon the need to maintain a positive world economic dynamics for the sake of the well-being of the entire human society, as recorded in the G-20 memorandums of recent years. At the same time, it makes sense to pay special attention to the weighty arguments in favor of maintaining a relatively moderate rate of economic growth in the period of the twenties.

The first argument is quite understandable: the priorities of sustainable development dictate the feasibility of qualitative improvement of most of the existing markets with their limited resource growth. It becomes achievable as a result of a mutually complementary combination of two processes: the introduction of new technologies that minimize the cost of resources, and the widespread use of reproducible resources and the spreading of non-waste production in technologically "old" sectors.

The second no less significant argument: for the reproduction of the potential of the mature post-industrial economy, the maximum quantitative growth of new technologies and new technology is not required. For example, the demand for new information digital technologies and computers will be limited, at least in terms of the number of their customers. In addition to this, one should take into account that, according to all forecasts, in the twenties the tendency of relative cheapening of technology will increase (in terms of the ratio of selling prices and useful effect).

Also in this perspective, probably, there will not be a need for a very rapid growth in the physical volumes of buildings, structures and other objects of the infrastructure of the postindustrial sector. The compactness and ergonomics of most of the high-tech enterprises with the continuation of the trend of miniaturization of technological progress is a very weighty argument in favor of this assumption.

As for personal and family welfare, the direction of the transformation of its structure in the long term will most likely predetermine changes in rational consumer preferences. The value of the quality of life in the environment conditions of the 21st century comes to the forefront. It involves a rational personal consumption of resources that does not harm the environment, and thus a rejection of wasteful consumption. Awareness of the uselessness of using for the sake of prestigious reasons a lot of cars, suburban buildings for the construction of which a huge mass of "brown" building materials is used, and other attributes of luxury life that are harmful to the environment, will become, perhaps, a fundamental feature of the future consumer ideology.

Finally, another weighty argument against the maximization of economic growth is due to the expectation of further institutional improvement in the main domestic markets in non-Western countries. According to all projections, in the considered perspective the rate of profit in real sectors of their economies will decrease and will approach the existing level in Western countries. It will first happen in China, then in other Asian giants and, ultimately, in most of the rest post developing countries. The rapid growth of most commodity markets caused by oppor-

tunistic and, especially, speculatively financial factors, will not be observed and, accordingly, market participants will not have an interest in maximizing the accumulation of capital.

And, probably, it is necessary to put a dot over and. Sustainable reproduction of the future world economy of the post-industrial type in the twenties suggests its stable and calm, absolutely non-explosive growth. At the same time, the rapid growth of individual markets, especially innovative ones, will be quite real.

However, as if in the end of the economic theme it is appropriate to make an important observation. Sustained favorable economic changes, objectively achievable in large part due to a purposeful national or supranational economic policy, should not be interpreted as ideal or perfectionist processes. They serve as necessary conditions for the implementation in principle of the most effective resource and institutional shifts initiated by the optimal initiative initiatives of the market agents themselves in terms of the implementation of technological innovations and a wide variety of investments, the use of productive capacity and qualified personnel.

3. Sustainable system transformation at the political field

Let us now dwell on the very fragmentally studied topic of sustainable transformation in the political field. It involves not only internal political stability, which is usually considered as a condition for maintaining the favorable economic development of certain countries.

Undoubtedly, the position in favor of the formation at the global level of a multipolar political order is incompatible with the hegemony of one country or group of countries, as well as with a superpower duopoly (the United States and its closest allies, on the one hand, and China and Russia, on the other). Such an anti-hegemonic order can become the basis for satisfying the national interests of small countries.

It will be necessary to create flexible, time-mobile institutional mechanisms, including organizational structures, ensuring international security. Besides an inalienable condition for global political stability is the real acceptance of the international legal regime.

Institutions providing sustainable internal political transformation of individual countries on the principles of democratization and competition are well known. According to national studies, the effectiveness within the political institutions directly depends on the quality of administrative management at all its levels.

The positive impact of the formation of a sustainable economic order on transformation in the political space will first manifest itself in the long-predicted shift. The political elite will be mainly replenished by higher management in the innovative and high-tech corporate sectors, as well as in the sectors of the new economy of reproducible resources, while reducing the presence of leaders of financial and trade capital.

At the same time, it worth noting that the achievement of a sustainable trajectory of political transformation would not mean a general transition to a perfect regime of democratic governance in civil society in accordance with traditional ideas. Especially in relation to countries that are not democratic in reality. Nevertheless, there will be grounds to hope for an irreversible endorsement of parliamentary democracy in place of a populist, permanently primeval form of presidential rule in this large group of countries.

4. Sustainable societal system transformation

Now let us turn to the extremely multifaceted problem of sustainable transformation on the societal field. Its integrative criteria condition, following the recognized notions, considers the fair distribution of wealth in its broad sense (including consumption of natural and cultural goods, education) among all generations of citizens accompanied a constant improvement of quality of life with reliable social balance.

This kind of transformation should be associated with gradual positive improvements in the status pyramid especially non-deviating strengthening of the middle class positions. Then, in the case of the parallel formation of a sustainable economic order, the composition of higher status groups (including the so-called transnational corporate class) will constantly update.

However, it is worth acknowledging that realistic design of improvements to the status pyramid of society represents a very complex problem. To solve it, it would be necessary to assess the impact on the status pyramid transformation of economic and political institutional progress, as well as the impact of technological and other exogenous off-system changes.

Crucial value, as the practical experience suggests, will be the realization of the synergic effect of mutually complementary decisions in different areas of social policy with the inherent participation of business and public independent organizations. Surely, the expected progress in the field of combating poverty and in the educational sphere is called to materialize in a significant improvement of the natural environment. In turn, it is extremely important to achieve the opposite effect of these improvements on the state of the entire national society. The favorable ecological conditions of life manifest as the weighty factors of the life stability in local communities and, consequently, of social stability in certain national borders, when the principle "to live at home, rather than to seek abroad" triumphs.

Judging by today's experience, the stimulation of various forms of voluntary participation of citizens in public activity becomes critical. It prevents social exclusion of certain groups of the population, in particular, the spread of youth drug addiction. Mass participation of migrants in the activities of public organizations is also of great importance, for which special educational and cultural programs are extremely necessary.

Ultimately, the satisfaction of the growing intellectual, moral and spiritual demands of citizens of modern countries presupposes a favorable cultural transformation while maintaining the divergence of national (subnational) cultures. Social policy along the lines of a sustainable system transformation should promote the orderly strengthening of the solidarity in society. Then, despite possible problem demographic and migration trends, the much-desired tightening of the integration of various national communities will be achievable.

It is also reasonable to count on the widest distribution of post-materialistic consciousness among representatives of educated and ensured strata of society. Their preferences will predetermine by values expressed in freedom of expression and quality of life. Post materialists put personal entrepreneurial success and the accumulation of individual wealth along with professional achievements and long-term well-being within the human and natural environment. Besides, entrepreneurs who share this ideology will guide by the social recognition of their sustainably effective business.

However, it would be a mistake to succumb in short mind manner to the illusion of a quite favorable social arrangement for the future. In the twenties, despite the likely spread of the post-materialist worldview, there is every reason to expect an expansion of routine, completely non-creative economic and other social activities in the conditions of using unoccupied digital-led technologies and robot technologies. A huge number, and possibly most of the employed, will be concentrated in low-tech and medium-tech activities in the service sector. The threat of preserving the non-creative needs in the life of these employers will become very significant.

Apparently, the way out to the decisive extent connects with the possibility of a radical increase in employment, including the work of intellectual workers, in the social environmental sector, where there will be a wide area for the use of new technological innovations as public goods. This process is designed to become comprehensive, covering both the growing megacities and ordinary cities, as well as the climatically challenging regions of the planet.

5. Optimistic conclusion

Sustainable overall social transformation in its main interconnected fields performs as an indispensable attribute of future human progress. Despite the likely weightiest costs and significant counter actions, the need for transition to this type of social development looks unambiguous.

A purposefully maintained movement along the trajectories of a sustainable social system transformation is by no means a path into a "bright future" in the spirit of communist ideology. New burning problems will arise before the planetary community. Definitely implementation of strategic plans of progressive development, at first place sustainable development, in the period of the twenties will come across serious various obstacles - sources of risks. Suffice it to say

about the threats of tech-gen disasters (the uprising of robots with artificial intelligence is no longer exclusively a topic of fantasy literature), unexplored before epidemics and ethno-national conflicts. However, these obstacles, if the ideology and practice of sustainable development has established, will be overcome in an acceptable way without long crises and immense social damage, on the base of global, regional and national consensus.

In regards to individual countries, the substantiation of realistic feasible support for the main areas of the sustainable social system transformation will be an important initial step towards the development of a national development strategy. Judging by international experience, it is definitely expedient to fix the benchmarks of sustainable transformation and other transformations within the framework of the system development strategy embracing the whole society. It calls for the identification of ways to achieve the future, which the majority of the national society desires and deserves (!).

Surely, it is worthwhile to remain realistic. Processes of deliberately unstable, accelerated transformational changes are called upon to account within the certain directions of the national development. For this purpose, special strategic approaches should approbate in practice.

The implementation of overall social transformation national strategies can provide the positive impact on the current design practice and public monitoring of the selected SD targets under the aegis of the UN [The Sustainable Development 2018, Global responsibilities 2018]. Due to the integration of these strategies, the possibilities of achieving these benchmarks in time as well as in space can assess for different countries and at the global level.

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